

REPORT

OF EVIDENCE OF PRODUCTS GENERATED

MAICC

Malla Abierta de iniciativas de
Ciencia Ciudadana

Translation: MAICC, Open Mesh of Citizen Science initiatives

Platform access:

<https://www.maicc-umbral.net/>

Novus

Home

About

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Access the platform

Open Mesh of Citizen Science Initiatives (MAICC)

MAICC Its objective is to build knowledge about Citizen Science and develop complex thinking skills in citizens, through their participation in the evaluation of real projects through a technological platform.

[Learn more >](#)

MAICC is a proposal from the Institute for the Future of Education, through the R4C Interdisciplinary Research Group that invites you to explore the world of Citizen Science at its finest. Here, we offer you the opportunity to delve into real research projects, where your participation will play a crucial role in their validation and success.

EVALUATION PATHWAY FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

Welcome to MAICC Pamela

Welcome! Here they will learn to evaluate collaborative and participatory scientific projects.

FIRST ACTIVITY

ASSIGNMENT AND ANALYSIS OF CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECT

Progress 33%

MAICC | Project

Pretest > My projects > Project information

About the *Citizen Science project: Get Involved - LibGuides*

Instructions
Below you will find general details about the assigned project. Your task will be to analyze this information and deepen your understanding by thoroughly researching the project to complete the "Metadata" section.

Alexa Day Create Lab - Speck and Smell Pittsburgh
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C-ZK8Fx8Erw>

Metadata
Once you have fully understood the assigned project, continue filling out the form below. Click the button to start.

Aim N/A	Investigator Affiliation N/A	Fund name N/A
Name of organizations N/A	Project application location N/A	Propellers N/A
Target users N/A	Thematic area N/A	Type of activity N/A
Application environment N/A	Mobile app N/A	Artifacts N/A
Vehicles N/A	Spaces N/A	Instruments N/A
Point of differentiation N/A	What are the research questions? N/A	What data or information analysis method is applied in the project? N/A
What data or information is collected in the project? N/A	How is data collected in the project? N/A	How is the quality of the data collected guaranteed? N/A
Materials N/A	Location of researchers N/A	Digital resources N/A
	Other actors involved N/A	

In the first activity the student participant recognises the randomly assigned citizen science project and is provided with a video, as an introduction. Then, he/she is asked to go deeper into the research of the same project to complete the fields in the Metadata section. This task aims to identify and document specific features and elements of the project.

SECOND ACTIVITY

CLASSIFICATION OF THE ASSIGNED PROJECT BASED ON THE CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECT THRESHOLD*

Instructions

Using your current understanding of the project, your next step is to recognize its elements: such as context awareness, citizen participation, among others; and then categorize them into one of these dimensions: Limited CC, Threshold CC, or Full Cycle CC. Be sure to back up each rating with concrete evidence and data. If you feel unsure about the validation of any component, we recommend expanding your research to make informed decisions.

Consult the article here to understand the evaluation typology: Threshold for citizen science projects.
<https://revistas.uned.es/index.php/ried/article/view/33052/25492>

Dimensions		Limited CC (Baseline-inputs)	CC Threshold (Transition products/results)	CC Full Cycle (Impact Compliance)
Context awareness	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Participation or replication of an existing project.	Improvement of an existing project	Release of an original theme project
Citizen involvement	<input type="radio"/>	Passive; follow a leader	Co-create a proposal	Lead a project
Infrastructure utilization	<input type="radio"/>	No or minimal interaction with the available infrastructure	Moderate interactions within available infrastructure	Improve interactions within the infrastructure
Technological innovation	<input type="radio"/>	Passive use of low-level technology	Technology adaptation	Creation of technology and/or use of advanced technologies.
Educational innovation	<input type="radio"/>	Lack of educational focus	Increase the use of educational resources	Proposes reusable resources for formal/non-formal education
Scope and Scale	<input type="radio"/>	Number of participants: local Number of places where data is collected: local	Number of participants: national Number of places where data is collected: national	Number of participants: worldwide Number of places where data is collected: worldwide
Networking	<input type="radio"/>	One or two propellers	Interaction of three helices	Integration of four to five helices that concludes with Public Policies
Complex thinking	<input type="radio"/>	None or only one of the sub-competencies is developed.	Two or three of the sub-competencies are developed.	The four sub-competencies are developed.

In the second activity, the student is asked to rank the assigned project according to the components of the threshold*. Prior research will enable him/her to justify the ranking decisions he/she makes.

* Sanabria-Z, J. C., Molina Espinosa, J. M., Alfaro Ponce, B., & Vycudiliková-Outlá, M. . (2022). Umbral para proyectos de ciencia ciudadana: el pensamiento complejo como impulsor de desarrollo holístico. *RIED-Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia*, 25(2), 113-131. <https://doi.org/10.5944/ried.25.2.33052>

THIRD ACTIVIDAD

QUALITATIVE REPORT OF THE ASSIGNED PROJECT

Home > Pretest > My projects > Project information > Assessment > Report

Report

Instructions

During this activity, we invite you to respond clearly and in detail to each and every one of the guiding questions provided.

In your own words, how would you describe the goal of the Citizen Science project you analyzed?

Approximately how much time did you spend analyzing and evaluating the project?

What are the strengths and weaknesses that you identified in the project?

If you had the opportunity, would you participate in the project you analyzed? But because?

After the analysis carried out, what learnings do you take away?

What recommendations would you make to the project designers/researchers to improve its operation?

Keep

In the Report activity, students are asked to respond to a series of guiding questions. This exercise seeks to gain a qualitative perspective on the previous activities and allows students to express their perception of the assigned project.

FOURTH ACTIVITY

OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE DESIGN (INFOGRAPHIC)

Home > Pretest > My projects > Project information > Assessment > Report > REA

Open Educational Resource (OER)

Instructions
 Directions: In this last activity, you will share the findings of your research and evaluation through an infographic. To achieve effective communication, you will design an infographic that includes the items indicated below. You can carry out the design on external platforms for the design of infographics such as: Canva, Infogram, PiktoChart, Genially, Vengage, Miro, among others. After you have the design, export the infographic in high-quality formats (such as PNG or PDF) and upload it to the appropriate space.

Here are some examples of impressive infographics for your inspiration:

- The Infographic Design Report: Trends to Try in 2023
- 40 of the best infographics to inspire you
- The 100 Best Infographics

Qualification
 Define a clear and concise title that describes the topic of the infographic

Develop your answer here

Header or subtitle
 The heading or subheading may summarize the purpose of the evaluation of the assigned citizen science project.

Develop your answer here

Introduction
 Include a brief introduction that contextualizes the citizen science project and its importance (maximum 400 characters).

Develop your answer here

Participants
 Provides information about those who participated in the project, such as scientists, volunteers and the community at large.

Develop your answer here

Project process (methodology)
 It describes the process followed in the citizen science project, from how the data is collected to how it is evaluated and how it is communicated. It is advisable to provide specific details regarding the steps taken in presenting this information.

Develop your answer here

Key Results
 Summary of the most important results of the project and their implications.

Develop your answer here

Impact and Benefits
 Information about the impact of the project on the community and science in general.

Develop your answer here

References and sources:
 List in APA format the references and sources consulted for the evaluation of the project.

Develop your answer here

Upload the PDF of the infographic you created here.

select your file

Upload the PDF of the infographic you created here. Note: this is the final version that you designed in an external tool.

select your file

MAICC 2024

In the Open Educational Resource activity, the aim is for students to gather key information to design an infographic about the assigned project, thus promoting effective data synthesis and visualisation. They are provided with design tool recommendations to facilitate the creation of the infographic, improving their skills in visual communication of scientific information.

FIFTH ACTIVITY

APPROVAL BY RESEARCHERS

As a final step, the work done by the students is reviewed and validated by the researchers involved in the project. The researcher can share annotations to the student's activity. Once validated, the student is notified that they have successfully completed their work of analysis and assessment of a citizen science project.

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